

SIMULATION OF NONISOTHERMAL LOW PRESSURE INFILTRATION PROCESSING

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SUMMARY: Pressure infiltration processing constitutes an attractive method to produce Metal Matrix Composites (MMC). It consists in injection under external pressure and solidification of a molten metal into a porous preform constituting the reinforcing ceramic phase. Optimization of mold filling kinetics and soundness of the part requires modeling of the coupled phenomena of fluid flow and heat transfer. This paper presents a model for nonisothermal low pressure infiltration processing. The coupled phenomena are written using a homogenization approach on the mass and energy conservation equations. The Finite Element Method is used to solve the resulting set of equations and boundary conditions. So far, isothermal infiltration at a temperature higher than the melting point and subsequent directional solidification are simulated.

KEYWORDS: metal matrix composites, infiltration, modeling, solidification, multiphase flow, permeability, saturation, homogenization

INTRODUCTION

Low pressure gas infiltration processing constitutes a simple and attractive method among the various methods for the production of Metal Matrix Composite materials. Liquid metal is injected in the pores of a ceramic preform consisting of consolidated fibers, particles or whiskers. Compared to other methods using metal in the liquid state, infiltration processing allows the manufacturing of partially reinforced parts and near net-shape parts while using rather conventional foundry practice.

During infiltration, physical, mechanical and chemical phenomena interplay, including multiphase flow of air and liquid metal in a porous medium, metal solidification, mechanical interaction and chemical interfacial reactions between fibers and matrix. These phenomena have now been identified, and solutions of the governing equations have been given analytically for simple geometries and boundary conditions [1][2]. More complex cases and their solutions have been described

Figure 1: *Schematic description of the homogenization approach*

using Finite Elements [3] or Finite Differences [4]. There is however still a need for tools available to treat cases closer to industrial practice, including infiltration under varying applied pressure functions and taking into account gradual mold filling and solidification.

In this paper, we present a Finite Element model under development to solve nonisothermal and nonsaturated metal flow in a porous fiber preform, including solidification. Fluid flow in infiltration is in general physically similar to a drainage experiment in soil mechanics, where a non wetting fluid displaces a wetting one. This similarity is used and GEFDYN Finite Element Code [5] developed at Ecole Centrale Paris for unsaturated soil mechanics is chosen as a basis for the development of the numerical simulation. In a first step, the code was adapted and validated for simulation of isothermal infiltration under an increasing applied pressure function. Heat flow was then introduced and validated in cases with no convection. The complete coupled simulation code is currently being developed.

MODELING

Three phases coexist during infiltration: metal, air and fibers. Metal is considered as a single phase, its state (liquid or solid) is dictated by its enthalpy which defines a dimensionless parameter g_s , corresponding to the volume fraction of solid metal with respect to the metal phase.

The following assumptions are considered for simplicity and because of their justification in many practical cases: the system is supposed to be chemically inert and the metal is assumed to be the non-wetting phase. In addition, we restrict our analysis to cases where mechanical terms are negligible. This assumption of metal and preform incompressibility has been shown to be valid for low pressure gas infiltration processing, but needs verification for each case.

Nonisothermal infiltration processing is described using a coupled formulation based on the Mass Conservation Equation and the Energy Conservation Equation. The approach is schematically represented in Fig. 1. We first define the local governing equation at each point of the space. After consideration of inter-phase boundary conditions, a homogenization procedure is used to provide macroscopically valid equations over a Representative Elementary Volume (REV).

Point Conservation Equations

The mass conservation equations for a phase α (α being metal, fibers or air) is written as [6]:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \rho_\alpha + \nabla(\rho_\alpha \cdot \mathbf{v}_\alpha) = 0 \quad (1)$$

energy is written in terms of specific enthalpy [6]:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t}(\rho_\alpha \cdot h_\alpha) - \frac{\partial}{\partial t}p_\alpha + \nabla(\rho_\alpha \cdot h_\alpha \cdot \mathbf{v}_\alpha) + \nabla \mathbf{q}_\alpha - \mathbf{v}_\alpha \cdot \nabla p_\alpha = 0 \quad (2)$$

where h_α , p_α and \mathbf{q}_α are respectively the specific enthalpy, the pressure and the heat flow vector in the α phase.

Boundary Conditions at the Interfaces

We restrict our analysis to the case where each of the 3 types of interface, Γ_{fm} , (fiber-metal interface), Γ_{fa} (fiber-air interface) and Γ_{am} (air-metal interface) are perfect (no interfacial reaction, instantaneous heat transfer, no slip). The stress tensor in the rigid fibers is considered to be isotropic and no shear is admitted. The boundary conditions for each $\alpha\beta$ interface, where α and β can be air, metal and fibers, are thus written:

$$\mathbf{q}_\alpha \cdot \mathbf{n}_{\alpha\beta} + \mathbf{q}_\beta \cdot \mathbf{n}_{\beta\alpha} = 0 \quad (3)$$

$$\mathbf{v}_\alpha \cdot \mathbf{n}_{\alpha\beta} + \mathbf{v}_\beta \cdot \mathbf{n}_{\beta\alpha} = 0 \quad (4)$$

$$T_\alpha = T_\beta \quad (5)$$

$$p_\alpha = p_\beta \quad (6)$$

where T_α is the temperature of the α -phase and $\mathbf{n}_{\alpha\beta}$ is the normal vector to the interface, pointing outwards from the α - into the β -phase.

Volume Averaged Equations

In a third step, a classical homogenization approach is applied to obtain a macroscopic mass and energy balance valid over a REV as shown in Fig. 1. In our case, restricting the problem as described above to perfect interfaces between each phase, all interfacial terms disappear. The volume averaged mass conservation equation is thus written as:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \langle \rho_m \rangle + \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \langle \rho_f \rangle + \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \langle \rho_a \rangle + \nabla \langle \rho_m \cdot \mathbf{v}_m \rangle + \nabla \langle \rho_f \cdot \mathbf{v}_f \rangle + \nabla \langle \rho_a \cdot \mathbf{v}_a \rangle = 0 \quad (7)$$

where $\langle \rho_m \rangle$ designates $\frac{1}{\Omega} \int_{\Omega_m} \rho_m d\Omega$, Ω being the REV and Ω_m being the volume in the REV occupied by the metal.

The volume averaged energy conservation equation is written as:

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \langle \rho_m \cdot h_m \rangle + \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \langle \rho_f \cdot h_f \rangle + \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \langle \rho_a \cdot h_a \rangle \\ & - \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \langle p_m \rangle - \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \langle p_f \rangle - \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \langle p_a \rangle + \nabla \langle \mathbf{q}_m \rangle + \nabla \langle \mathbf{q}_f \rangle + \nabla \langle \mathbf{q}_a \rangle \\ & + \nabla \langle \rho_m \cdot h_m \cdot \mathbf{v}_m \rangle + \nabla \langle \rho_f \cdot h_f \cdot \mathbf{v}_f \rangle + \nabla \langle \rho_a \cdot h_a \cdot \mathbf{v}_a \rangle \\ & - \langle p_m \rangle \cdot \nabla \langle \mathbf{v}_m \rangle - \langle p_f \rangle \cdot \nabla \langle \mathbf{v}_f \rangle - \langle p_a \rangle \cdot \nabla \langle \mathbf{v}_a \rangle = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Solution

The system of equations 7 and 8 describes infiltration processing in most general terms. Additional information is required to obtain a solution, in terms that correspond to practical engineering aspects.

The volume fraction of each α phase is therefore defined as $\theta_\alpha = \frac{\Omega_\alpha(t)}{\Omega}$, the volume occupied by the phase over the volume of the REV. In addition, macroscopic values are used to represent the averages, for example: $\langle \rho_m \rangle = \theta_m \cdot \langle \rho_m \rangle^m = \theta_m \cdot \rho_m$

Pressure p and metal enthalpy H_m are chosen as the functions to be mapped over space and time, whereby $H_m = \langle h_m \cdot \rho_m \rangle^m$ is the metal enthalpy which is classically measured when doing calorimetric experiments.

Since the preform is supposed to be incompressible, the fiber volume fraction θ_f is constant. By similarity with soil mechanics the saturation S is introduced as:

$$S = \frac{\theta_m}{1 - \theta_f} \quad (9)$$

In a first approach, capillary phenomena and heat flow phenomena are decoupled. The saturation in metal phase is thus assumed to be a function of metal pressure only and not of enthalpy. Similarly, the volume fraction of solid metal g_s is assumed to depend only on metal enthalpy, and not on pressure.

We introduce Darcy's law which describes macroscopically fluid flow for a newtonian fluid in a porous medium. We suppose that only the liquid metal is moving, hence that $\langle v_m \rangle = \langle v_{ml} \rangle^m \cdot \theta_m \cdot (1 - g_s)$ and write:

$$\mathbf{v} = \mathbf{v}_{ml} \cdot \theta_m \cdot (1 - g_s) = -\mathbf{K} \cdot (\nabla p - \rho \cdot \mathbf{g}) \quad (10)$$

where \mathbf{v} is the Darcy velocity for laminar fluid flow of the metal phase (its liquid volume fraction) in a porous medium and \mathbf{g} is gravity. The analysis is therefore restricted to cases of laminar flow. Permeability is written as:

$$\mathbf{K} = \frac{\mathbf{K}_s \cdot K_r \cdot K_{g_s}}{\mu} \quad (11)$$

where \mathbf{K}_s is the specific permeability tensor [m^2], K_r is the relative permeability due to multiphase flow, K_{g_s} is the relative permeability due to partial solidification and μ is the metal viscosity [$\text{Pa} \cdot \text{s}$]. In addition we consider Fourier's law as valid in a macroscopic sense:

$$\mathbf{q} = -\mathbf{k}_{\text{eff}} \cdot \nabla T \quad (12)$$

where the effective heat conductivity \mathbf{k}_{eff} is calculated using rule of mixture laws depending on the different volume fractions and their orientation as proposed in [1] or [7]. Fiber enthalpy is expressed as a function of metal enthalpy:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} H_f = \frac{dH_f}{dH_m} \cdot \frac{\partial}{\partial t} H_m \quad (13)$$

and the temperature gradient as:

$$\nabla T = \nabla \left(\frac{dT}{dH_m} \cdot H_m \right) \quad (14)$$

the air phase are neglected, as well as deviatory terms in the averages. The terms $\langle p_\alpha \rangle \cdot \nabla \langle \mathbf{v}_\alpha \rangle$ and $\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \langle p_\alpha \rangle$ in the energy conservation equation are neglected for the present case of low pressure infiltration, as well.

The resulting equations are then:

$$(1 - \theta_f) \cdot \frac{\partial}{\partial t}(S \cdot \rho_m) - \nabla(\rho_m \cdot \mathbf{K} \cdot \nabla p) = 0 \quad (15)$$

and:

$$(1 - \theta_f) \cdot \frac{\partial}{\partial t}(S \cdot H_m) + \theta_f \cdot \frac{dH_f}{dH_m} \cdot \frac{\partial}{\partial t}H_m - \nabla((1 - g_s) \cdot H_m \cdot \mathbf{K} \cdot \nabla p) - \nabla(\mathbf{k}_{\text{eff}} \cdot \nabla(\frac{dT}{dH_m} \cdot H_m)) = 0 \quad (16)$$

In applying derivative principles, the final mass conservation equation is obtained:

$$(1 - \theta_f) \cdot \rho_m \cdot \frac{dS}{dp} \cdot \frac{\partial}{\partial t}p + (1 - \theta_f) \cdot S \cdot \frac{d\rho_m}{dH_m} \cdot \frac{\partial}{\partial t}H_m - \rho_m \cdot \nabla(\mathbf{K} \cdot \nabla p) - \frac{d\rho_m}{dH_m} \cdot (\mathbf{K} \cdot \nabla p) \cdot \nabla H_m = 0 \quad (17)$$

The first and the second term represent mass storage terms due to saturation change and metal density change. Terms three and four are flow terms due to Darcian flow and due to metal density change inducing flow.

The energy conservation equation becomes:

$$((1 - \theta_f) \cdot S + \theta_f \cdot \frac{dH_f}{dH_m}) \cdot \frac{\partial}{\partial t}H_m + (1 - \theta_f) \cdot \frac{dS}{dp} \cdot H_m \frac{\partial}{\partial t}p - (1 - g_s) \cdot H_m \cdot \nabla(\mathbf{K} \cdot \nabla p) - (1 - g_s - H_m \cdot \frac{\partial g_s}{\partial H_m}) \cdot (\mathbf{K} \cdot \nabla p) \cdot \nabla H_m - \nabla(\mathbf{k}_{\text{eff}} \cdot \nabla(\frac{dT}{dH_m} \cdot H_m)) = 0 \quad (18)$$

The first term constitutes an energy storage term due to enthalpy change (temperature change) in fibers and metal. The second term describes the energy storage term due to saturation change. The third term is the classical convection term. The fourth term is an energy flow term due do enthalpy gradients and Darcian flow and the fifth term is the classical energy conduction term.

Numerical Solution

The problem is strongly non-linear. In addition, a solution should be provided for any geometry and boundary condition. For these two reasons a numerical approach must be taken. The Finite Element code GEFDYN [5] is chosen as a basis. This software was developed to model 2D and 3D non-saturated fluid flow in deformable porous media and saturated thermal consolidation neglecting the convection in heat transfer and not taking into account phase change. A new version is proposed introducing the coupling between fluid flow and heat transfer, to take into account metal solidification during flow, either by heat exchange with the fibers, or by contact with the mold walls.

The complete formulation introducing the energy conservation equation will be described in Ref. 8. The numerical procedure applying a classical Galerkin method for space discretization, an implicit Euler method for time discretization and a modified Newton method for the iterative solution of the non linear problem is described in Ref. 5.

Figure 2: Schematic drawing of the experimental configuration. The copper chill is represented by a horizontal bar which can be placed in contact with the mould

Figure 3: Schematic drawing of the Finite Element grid: 19 * 12 elements in 2D axisymmetric configuration. In addition, different regions of boundary conditions are shown in different colours

The terms described in equations 17 and 18 have been introduced into the code and are currently under investigation. First results are obtained at present for the decoupled cases of isothermal infiltration and subsequent solidification considering a constant metal density. The simplified equations, taking into account the terms 1 and 3 of the mass and 1 and 5 of the energy conservation equation can nevertheless already be applied to simulate industrial cases.

APPLICATION TO INFILTRATION PROCESSING

The FEM code is validated for isothermal infiltration, and solidification without convection. A case study is thus proposed here to illustrate the predicting capability of the current program, and its applicability to industrially relevant processing methods.

Problem Description

A 24% volume fraction Saffil® 0.1cm short fiber preform is infiltrated under gas pressure by pure (99,85%) aluminum. The proposed processing route is to isothermally infiltrate the preform, using a two-step pressure function to minimize preform compression. After infiltration is complete, the sample is directionally solidified by contact with a water cooled copper chill.

A schematic representation of the infiltration set-up is shown in Fig. 2. The Saffil preform is a disk, 95 mm in diameter, and 30 mm high, encased in a graphite mold. Infiltration occurs through a 15 mm diameter circular gate on top of the preform disk.

The pressure function which is applied at the metal entrance gate is given in Fig. 4. Pressure is kept low (0,8 MPa) during the first 20 seconds to prevent preform damage while allowing metal flow within the entire preform. Pressure is then increased to 3.0 MPa to allow complete filling of the smaller pores.

The temperature curve (applied as a boundary condition on the lower border of the sample) is given in Fig. 5. During the short infiltration time of 40 s, temperature can be considered as constant at 700°C (experiments showed a temperature decrease of about 5-10°C during infiltration). The sample then comes in contact with a copper chill, the boundary condition is approximated by a perfect contact and a temperature of 25°C neglecting the graphite mold. In this case of directional

Figure 4: *Pressure curves for simulation - time levels optimized using GEFDYN*

Figure 5: *Temperature curves for simulation - idealized, more complex cases can easily be studied*

solidification, the assumption of a constant metal density is a simplification of the real mechanism (contraction of metal is filled up by the metal feeder on top of the preform), but should yield fairly good agreement with experimental results.

Simulation Results

Simulation was performed using the grid shown in Fig. 3. The materials parameters for simulation of infiltration are chosen as described in Ref. 3. The thermal parameters are taken from Ref. 4. The effective thermal conductivity of the composite is calculated by a rule of mixture proposed in Ref. 1 for conduction perpendicular to the fibers.

Porosity curves

At the beginning, the preform is completely empty, the porosity is hence 76%. Fig. 6 shows the distribution of porosity after 5, 13 and 30 seconds. Infiltration progresses gradually in a semielliptic way, because the permeabilities are different in the 2 directions of the nonisotropic preform. After 5 seconds, the front has advanced 40 mm in the x direction and 25 mm in the z direction. After 13 seconds, the infiltration front has reached the mold walls, but porosity is not yet uniform. This is the case some seconds later (not shown here), when the porosity is uniform according to the applied pressure of 0.8 MPa, about 7%. The subsequent pressure increase from 20 to 30 seconds (see Fig. 4) reduces porosity to about 2% as seen on the right hand side of Fig. 6.

Temperature curves

Until 40 seconds, temperature was maintained constant. The sample is then placed in contact with the cooled copper plate. Cooling initiates at $z = 30$ mm (according to Fig. 2). The resulting temperature distributions are given in figure 7 in which the z-axis has been inverted compared to Fig. 6 for better visibility. After 43 seconds, the solidification front has advanced 24 mm (this corresponds to the change in slope in Fig. 7), and after 50 seconds, all the composite material is in solid state at a maximum temperature of 350°C . At the end of the simulation (after 80 seconds, not shown here), temperature is uniform in the preform at 25° .

The curves have been tested against real infiltration experiments (for porosity, [3]) and analytical solutions (for temperature, [9]) and show good coincidence.

Figure 6: Porosity distribution after 5.0, 13.0 and 40.0 s infiltration time, shown in a 3D diagram above the x-z plane

Figure 7: Temperature distribution after 43 and 50 s, corresponding to respectively 3 and 10 s cooling time

The present work gives a formulation of the physical laws governing nonisothermal infiltration processing including capillary phenomena. The resulting formulation consists of coupled terms which include mass and energy storage and flow including convection and conduction. These equations have been introduced in the Finite Element Code GEFDYN. The solution is now available for the modeling of one class of practical infiltration cases, when fiber preform and liquid metal are initially at the same temperature and when metal density is assumed to be constant. The introduction of solidification shrinkage is now under investigation.

Research on application of this problem to the case when both solidification and flow phenomena occur concomitantly is ongoing, but need of additional materials parameters will require further experimental studies or simplifying assumptions.

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